

GROUP-BASED NUTRITION PROGRAMS TO PROMOTE HEALTH AND MOBILITY IN COMMUNITY-DWELLING OLDER ADULTS: A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW

31 studies included

Publication years: 2010-2020

Participants

Community-dwelling
Aged 55+ years

Nutrition outcomes explored:

- Food & fluid intake
- Nutrition risk
- Healthy eating knowledge

Mobility outcomes explored:

- Physical activity
- Day-to-day activity

Types of group-based nutrition programs

Nutrition education & tools for change
e.g., goal setting, interactive cooking activities

Passive nutrition education

e.g., lectures, handouts

Food access

e.g., mobile markets, community gardens, food samples

Interactive nutrition education

e.g., workshops, discussions

Key messages/results

- Group-based nutrition education with tools for change (e.g., goal setting, interactive cooking activities) may increase healthy eating and reduce nutrition risk.
- The impact of nutrition programs on mobility outcomes is unclear.
- Overall, the body of evidence was of low quality with great variability in programs and outcomes reported.
- High-quality research in group-based nutrition programs to improve health and mobility for older adults is needed.

Teggart, K., et al. Group based nutrition interventions to promote health and mobility in community-dwelling older adults: A systematic review. 18 August 2021, PREPRINT (Version 1). <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-825757/v1>

Teggart, K., Ganann, R., Sihota, D., Moore, C., Keller, H., Senson, C., Phillips, S.M., Senson C, Adams J, Elliot A & Neil-Sztramko, S.E. (2021). Infographic: Group-based nutrition interventions to promote health and mobility in community-dwelling older adults: A systematic review

<https://achru.mcmaster.ca/research-studies/embolden-trial-partnering-older-adults-and-communities-develop-and-test-community>